

Re-Exploring the Soul of Maria in Paulo Coelho's Eleven Minutes

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Abstract

Paulo Coelho's novel Eleven minutes takes on a new look on the prostitutes. The author brings the nature of sex, including prostitution, and sex in marriages where the sex is somehow less than love, and the nature of human personal relationships in generally disappointing and enslaving. Coelho elevates in Eleven Minutes to passionate realm of love, sex and divinity. Coelho uses Maria to write a saga of sex and love-making and explores the difference between the two and questions various grounds of societal codes of morality and righteous living. This paper deals how Maria lost her soul and how she re-explored her soul.

Keywords: Identity, Explore, Soul, Love, Sex, Morality.

In Coelho's Eleven Minutes, Maria is a young girl who dreams for fame and fortune like many young girls. She dreams of getting married to a Prince Charming man and live in a lovely house happily ever after. Her first innocent encounter with love, leave her brokenhearted. At a tender age, she becomes convinced that she will never find true love, instead believing that love is a terrible thing that will make her suffer. In Rio she meets a Swiss man, who takes her to Geneva, and there she tries to attain her dream but she ends up working as a prostitute. Finally, she re-explored and re-discovered her soul and real love.

This paper focuses on the different levels of Eleven Minutes. Firstly, Coelho chooses sex and prostitution; two generally recognized taboo subject matter, to be the central themes of novel. In doing so, he intentionally breaks these taboos by extensively exploring them. Secondly, the fact that Maria's character is based on real life come across with prostitutes highlights Coelho's intention to make these marginalized women's voices heard through his narrative.

Maria was eleven; she fell in love with a boy. He was neighbour and accompanied her on the way to school. They never exchanged a single word but this was the best moments in her life. She found the weekends deadly dull. She was waiting for the boy to speak. One day the boy came to ask for pencil. She noticed that he was having pen. Maria's concentration in studies was disturbed but she had concentration on television. She had content herself with love and suffered in silence until the end of the school year. After holidays

the boy did not appear. She found that he has left the town. At that moment, Maria learned certain things are lost forever. She decided that she would follow the boy's footsteps. She had trust and hope that one day he will come and take her. But as the days passed she lost her trust.

Human beings are social beings. Without interrelation with society and with the cosmic world, humanity cannot realize its oneness with the universe. It is social interdependence that enables humans to test their faith and prove to themselves on the touchstone of reality. At the tender age Maria had negative experience of love and trust.

She decided to fall in love again when she was fifteen years old. Unfortunately, it was not long lasting because a boy cheated with her friend. Then, Maria suddenly realized that love was the only thing to make her fall apart. She was convinced that she would never find of true love, instead of believing that love is a terrible thing to make you suffer.

Maria's disappointment towards love accede her to start having curiosity with some sexual encounters. She had some sexual experiences in kissing, making love, even self-sex like masturbation. She thus started to deem that masturbation was an alternative way to intercourse, besides she discovered that it was more fascinating. Her sexual experiences let her lose interest in serious relationship with other boys. Then, she became an adventurous and discovered many discoveries.

Maria's adventurous took her to get a chance in Rio de Janeiro in pursuit of becoming model and film career. She was always very enticing, conscious of the power of her beauty. This beauty engrossed a Swiss man Roger. She tripped to Switzerland to Geneva, without her knowledge she signed in the contract paper. The Swiss man cheated her and gave a nominal amount only. She got fed up with him and ended it up by working as a high class prostitute. Drifting far away from love, she developed a fascination about sex such as enjoying her experiment in sadomasochism. It was one of Maria's self-transcendences became a destructor of soul. She was portrayed that intentionally destructed her soul and life. She was filled with frustration and depression.

Maria's depression leads her to prostitution. Prostitution is considered as destructing as system of slavery. Terrence is one of the Maria's clients. He treated her as a slave. She was naked, gagged, handcuffed and slapped by him. "Everyone needs to earn money but not everyone chooses to live on the margins of society. She was doing it because she had nothing to lose, because her life was one of constant, day-to-day frustration" (81). She is alienated not only from God and society but from herself also.

In the big cities, due to poverty most of the women are forced to the profession of prostitution. In rural areas caste system made them to do this work. Janina Gomes emphasis in her article, "Poverty, malnutrition, illiteracy, unsafe conditions of work, lack of health facilities, susceptibility to diseases, physical and sexual assaults by men, sometimes domestically, sometimes by upper class men, can be worse." (54)

Maria has chosen the prostitute life because of poverty and survives. In the article Literature and Morality Waugh points out, "I imply there is a moral purpose, a chance of salvation in every human life" (202). Likewise, Maria gets redemption and salvation from her immoral life. "Maria felt herself to be very wise" (256) because she discovered the true love. She mysteriously recovered her virginity. Maria's spirituality leads her into moral life by which she feels very proud and confident.

Throughout her journey, she portrayed as a sexual characteristics person. And she eventually found an ultimate truth about herself. After her adolescent frustration toward love, bringing Maria unto realizing that her love for a painter, named Ralf Hart. In this odyssey of self-discovery, Maria's spiritual realization paradoxically sends her into a difficult decision among pursuing path of darkness, sexual-pleasure, or risking everything to find her 'inner-light'. In this case, Maria through her self-transcendence as a creator, she experienced an eleven minutes of sacred-sex with

Hart. It was a depiction of sexual journey of prostitute yet it was Maria's transference as a creator. She found her true love with a man who treated her differently.

Maria's situation makes her a prostitute. She was in depression upset because there was no one to speak with her. None of them came up to her to say hello or to wish her success in her new profession. "Instead of feeling depressed, she felt proud, she was fighting for herself, she wasn't some helpless person" (74). The spiritual ethical allows the self to be bound together around transcendent values hope, purpose, fidelity, love and wisdom. In the other words, if one has achieved this image of spiritual adult, therefore spiritual identity is formed. Coelho has been aware of what he is and where his spiritual side leads him to, "Elevated passion and greater ability to connect with loved ones, God, and the cosmos were experienced...The after effects of the mystical experience revealed promotion of human functioning in relation to self, others, and God (MacKnee, 20)."

Maria, in being a prostitute permitted herself the journey of self-discovery. Life was teaching her very fast that only the strong species survive. She is different from other prostitutes; that is touching her client's soul:

"They wanted to talk about the pressures of work, about their unfaithful wife, about how lonely they felt, how they had no one to talk to. She needed to find some way of freeing her clients from the enormous pressure, this meant both improving the quality of her services and the chance of earning some extra money." (86-87)

It shows that Maria is having strong identity and she gave a new life, hope and faith to others whomever she meets. At the end of the six months, Maria had sixty thousand Swiss francs in a bank account. Her dreams are getting fulfilled; she gets fame and good fortune. When Maria eventually falls in love with Ralf, an artist who aids her journey of spiritual awakening, unsurprisingly she leaves her profession behind. The novel allows us to discover the world of a prostitute and to construct and reconstruct different images and understandings of binary oppositions such as man/woman, decent woman/prostitute, and mind/body.

Maria starts to write in her diary a week after her initiation into the world of prostitution – highlighting the importance of love for her or rather her soul;

"I'm not a body with a soul, I'm a soul that has a visible part called the body. All this week, contrary to what one might expect, I have been more conscious of the presence of this soul than usual. It didn't say anything to me, didn't criticise me or feel sorry for me: it merely watched me" (78).

Maria's initiation into the world of the body as a commodities object makes her think more and more of her soul and it intensifies the perceptiveness of her self-consciousness. The more she sinks into this world, the more she will be prominent to the world of soul. The main reason is her realization that love and soul are more important than sex and body: "I need to write about love. I need to think and think and write and write about love - otherwise, my soul won't survive" (79). The eleven minutes are devoted to the body and most of the forty five minutes is devoted to the soul. Again, Coelho gives the soul more importance in terms of time and the duration of the relation.

Maria's job is to "know precisely which points to touch - on both body and soul, but mainly the soul - give some advice on personal problems, be his friend for half an hour, of which eleven minutes would be spent . . ." (93). Love and soul take much prominence in the novel.

Loneliness was discussed much in the Eleven Minutes. Winne Yang mentions in his dissertation the percentage of lonely people in wealthy countries is higher than those in poor countries. Those who seem to possess everything are more likely to be lonely. It's ironic but true, they cannot trust people for they have too much to lose. Maria knew that she was not only felt lonely and alienated from society. "Human beings can withstand a week without water, two weeks without food, many

years of homelessness, but not loneliness. It is the worst of all tortures, the worst of all sufferings.” (94). Maria realized, “Like her, these men, and the many others who sought her company, were all tormented by that same destructive feeling, the sense that no one else on the planet cared about them.” (118)

She fights between body and soul. At last she came to the conclusion the real love is not an outside but it is inside. Author conveys that, sex can be enjoyable only when love, trust and honesty exist hand in hand. Sex is, after all what “Our bodies learn to speak the language of the soul, know as sex. Sex is a manifestation of a spiritual energy called love.” (222)

Coelho portrays the contemporary world of human life. He says that, this novel is the story of sacred prostitute. She became an observer not a doer. And, she could preserve her ‘special light’ (light of the soul), to be seen by Ralf Hart. Her soul was getting stronger while going through all types of pain and humiliation with her body, so much so that she could imagine herself “ as a soul that has a visible part called body.” (75). She came through different types of pain, one that awakened the body and gave pleasure but the other awakened the soul and led it to peace. She was aware of the fact that suffering if confronted without fear is the passport to freedom. She had discovered a door into a different level of consciousness, and there was no room now for anything but implacable nature and her invincible self.

Her journey from body consciousness to soul consciousness through body is, not straight. It has complex ways to lead up to the aim of self realization and ultimately the summit has been attained, a human summit with human body melting into spiritual consciousness of man. Self-discovery, self realization and self exploration lead Maria to attain her Soul. Ralf Hart helped her to attain her soul. She discovered a whole universe inside her own body. Paulo Coelho sums it up:

“... it wasn’t eleven minutes, it was an eternity, it was as if we had both left our bodies and were walking joyfully through the gardens of paradise in understanding and friendship. I was woman and man, he was man and woman. I don’t know how long it lasted, but everything seemed to be silent, at prayer, as if the universe and life had ceased to exist and become transformed into something sacred, nameless and timeless.” (264)

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